

DRAFT BRIGHTON COLLABORATION CASE DEFINITION LEVELS OF DIAGNOSTIC CERTAINTY (LOC) FOR ACUTE MULTI-ORGAN DYSFUNCTION (aMOD)

LOC	Criteria - Recent onset (≤ 7 days) required. All organs included in the case definition should be recent onset (≤ 7 days) and part of the same clinical episode
1	≥ 2 organs with definite dysfunction (LOC 1)
2	[1 organ with definite dysfunction (LOC 1) AND ≥ 1 organs with probable dysfunction (LOC 2)] OR ≥ 2 organs with probable dysfunction (LOC 2)
3	[1 organ with definite dysfunction (LOC 1) AND ≥ 1 organs with possible dysfunction (LOC 3)] OR [1 organ with probable dysfunction (LOC 2) AND ≥ 1 organs with possible dysfunction (LOC 3)] OR ≥ 2 organs with possible dysfunction (LOC 3)
4	Reported as a case of acute MOD but insufficient information to meet any defined level (i.e. LOC 1, 2, 3 or 5) of the case definition
5	NOT a case of acute MOD OR not of recent (≤ 7 days) onset OR MOD related to therapeutic medication or peri-procedural

Organ Dysfunction	Population	Level 1 - Definite	Level 2 - Probable	Level 3 - Possible
Respiratory dysfunction	Adult	Two consecutive measures (≥ 1 hr apart) of one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PaO₂/FiO₂ (mmHg) <300 • SaO₂/FiO₂ <315 OR Invasive/mechanical ventilation required for respiratory dysfunction	(Need for supplemental oxygen of at least > 4L/min via nasal canula AND requiring increasing respiratory support (any type) for > 1hr) to maintain saturation >94%	Two or more clinical signs of respiratory dysfunction: tachypnea, cyanosis, grunting, chest wall retractions, increased use of accessory respiratory muscles, newly identified SaO ₂ <94%
	Pediatric	Two consecutive measures (≥ 1 hr apart) of one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PaO₂/FiO₂ (mm Hg) <300 • SaO₂/FiO₂ <264 OR Invasive/mechanical ventilation required for respiratory dysfunction		
Cardiovascular dysfunction	Adult	Sustained administration of vasoactive agents ¹ (for ≥ 30 minutes) to maintain MAP ≥ 65 mmHg	Administration of intravenous fluids resuscitation of at least 500 ml intravenously for the purpose of maintaining MAP ≥ 65 mmHg	MAP ≤ 65 mmHg OR Two or more of the following: Low volume/ thready/ absent peripheral pulses, cold/clammy extremities, capillary refill time >3 sec
	Pediatric	Any need for vasoactive agents ¹ to maintain age specific MAP: <46 (<1 mo), <55 (1–11 mo), < 60 (12–23 mo), <62 (24–59 mo), <65 (60–143 mo), <67 (>144 mo)	Fluid resuscitation of at least 10ml/kg to maintain age specific MAP	One MAP less than age specific value OR Two or more of the following: Low volume/ thready/ absent peripheral pulses, cold/clammy extremities, capillary refill time >3 sec
Renal dysfunction	Adult	Increase in serum creatinine ≥ 2 times patient's baseline OR Increase in serum creatinine by ≥ 0.3 mg/dL (≥ 26.5 micromol/L) within 48 hrs OR Sustained reduction in urine output ² to <0.5 mL/kg/hour for ≥ 12 hours	Any serum creatinine greater than 1.2 mg/dL (in absence of baseline) OR Sustained reduction in urine output ² to <0.5 mL/kg/hour for at least 6 hours	Sustained reduced urine output for at least 24 hours ²

	Pediatric	Increase in serum creatinine to 2x patients' baseline OR Serum creatinine higher than the upper limit of age specific value (in absence of patients' baseline): 1.0–1.1 mg/dL (<1 mo), 0.5–0.7 (-11 mo), 0.6–1.0 (12–23 mo), 0.9–1.5 (24–59 mo), 1.1–1.7 (60–143 mo), 1.7–2.8 (144–216 mo), 2.0–3.4 (>216 mo) OR Sustained reduction in urine output ² to <0.5 mL/kg/hour for ≥12 hours.		
Encephalopathy⁴	Adult	[GCS ≤ 13 OR any one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreased or absent response to environment, as defined by response to loud noise or painful stimuli Decreased or absent eye contact Inconsistent or absent response to external stimuli Decreased arousability New onset seizure associated with loss of consciousness] AND Any one of the following for >24h: depressed level of consciousness, acute personality/behavior change ³	[GCS ≤ 13 OR any one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreased or absent response to environment, as defined by response to loud noise or painful stimuli Decreased or absent eye contact Inconsistent or absent response to external stimuli Decreased arousability New onset seizure associated with loss of consciousness] AND Any one of the following for 6-24 hrs: depressed level of consciousness, acute personality/behavior change ³	GCS ≤ 13 OR Deviation from alert status, including response only to verbal or painful stimuli, or complete unresponsiveness OR Any one of the following for >2hrs and <6 hrs: depressed level of consciousness, acute personality/behavior change ³ , new onset of seizure
	Pediatric	GCS ≤ 13 AND Any one of the following for >24h: depressed level of consciousness, irritability, new onset of seizure	GCS ≤ 13 AND Any one of the following for 6-24 hrs: depressed level of consciousness, irritability, new onset of seizure	Any one of the following for >2hrs and <6 hrs: depressed level of consciousness, irritability, new onset of seizure
Hepatic dysfunction	All ages: ages and pediatric	Total bilirubin ≥2x ULN (1.2 mg/dL or 20.5 micromol/L) OR ALT ≥3x ULN	Increased total bilirubin AND ALT/AST any value above normal range	Jaundice OR scleral icterus
Hemostatic dysfunction / Coagulopathy	All ages: ages and pediatric	Platelet count < 100,000 cells/μL OR INR ≥ 1.5 OR Fibrinogen ≤ 1.5 g/L OR D-dimer > 8 times ULN for the testing laboratory ⁵	Platelet count below normal range for the reporting lab OR INR above normal range OR Decreased fibrinogen below laboratory reference OR Elevated D-dimer above ULN	Any of the following signs of bleeding or thrombosis occurring spontaneously or unexplained: Bleeding: petechiae, purpura, ecchymosis, hemorrhagic oozing from cutaneous lesions, hematoma, bruising, hematemesis, hematochezia/melena, occult bleeding ⁶ per rectum, epistaxis, hemoptysis, hematuria, vaginal bleeding (non-menstrual), mucosal (e.g., conjunctival, gingival) bleeding, intracranial bleeding

				Thrombosis: digital ischemia, purpura fulminans, ischemic skin necrosis, clinically suspected venous or arterial thrombosis
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¹ Dopamine or Epinephrine or Norepinephrine or Vasopressin

² Reduction of urine output as observed by a clinician

³ Definition of personality/behavior change: irritability, aggression, impulsiveness, disinhibition, and emotional lability

⁴ Sedated patients should not be considered for Encephalopathy. Other organs should still be assessed for dysfunction.

⁵ Rare but serious occurrence

⁶ Invisible to eye, seen on fecal occult blood test

ALT = Alanine Aminotransferase, **AST** = Aspartate Aminotransferase, **FiO₂** = Fraction of inspired oxygen, **GCS** = Glasgow Coma Scale, **MAP** = Mean Arterial Pressure, **PaO₂** = Partial pressure of oxygen in arterial blood, **PT/INR** = Prothrombin Time / International Normalized Ratio, **SaO₂** = Arterial Oxygen Saturation, **ULN** = Upper limit normal